

THE IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES IN DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the role of the system of pedagogical sciences and the branches of psychology in the development of professional competencies for future primary school teachers. It is emphasized that every future primary school teacher should not only have an in-depth knowledge of specialized subjects but also a thorough understanding of related disciplines, enabling them to apply their theoretical knowledge in practice.*

Keywords: *professional competence, development of the student's personality, individual approach, pedagogical training, pedagogy, psychology, pedagogical didactic strategy, effective communication, pedagogical technology, devoted, well-rounded generation, system of pedagogical sciences, branches of psychology, pedagogical process, specialization, theoretical knowledge, practice.*

Introduction: The formation and development of the professional competencies of future primary school teachers play a significant role in the development of the education system in Uzbekistan. Pedagogical and psychological knowledge helps teachers to provide effective education, taking into account the individual characteristics of students. Pedagogical and psychological sciences are essential for enhancing the professional qualifications of future primary school teachers and preparing them to solve various educational tasks. The effective teaching of pedagogy and psychology within the framework of higher education institutions is of great importance for preparing competent, competitive, and qualified pedagogical personnel for the education system.

The Law on Education, adopted on September 23, 2020, emphasizes the content of education, the methods of teaching and upbringing used, educational technologies, as well as the results of students' mastery of subjects.

Currently, significant attention is being given to the fundamental reform of the education sector and improving the quality of pedagogical education. For this reason, higher education institutions that train pedagogical staff closely cooperate with the schools assigned to them, including preschools and general secondary education institutions. These institutions work together to prepare highly qualified pedagogical staff and organize continuous professional development for teachers. This collaboration also includes organizing master classes and student internships and providing methodological support to these institutions. It is essential to raise a knowledgeable, educated, independent, and analytical-thinking generation that is well-versed in their profession, cares for their country and people, and is dedicated, morally developed, physically strong, and healthy. Such an approach will contribute to securing the future of our nation.

Currently, the category of a teacher's professional competence holds one of the leading positions in meeting the modern demands of 21st-century teaching. Primary education is aimed at forming the foundations of literacy, knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary for continuing general secondary education. Pedagogical and psychological sciences play a key role in shaping the professional competencies of future primary school teachers. These disciplines ensure that teachers acquire specialized pedagogical and psychological knowledge, helping them work effectively with students and optimize the teaching process. The teacher's psychological and pedagogical knowledge is not only crucial for the students but also plays a significant role in the teacher's own professional development. These sciences provide the essential skills necessary for educating students and ensuring their all-around development.

The system of pedagogical sciences is aimed at ensuring personal development, as well as intellectual, moral-ethical, and physical development, by considering the specific characteristics of different age groups and the physiological and psychological state of the child.

For this reason, the integrated pedagogical process is studied by pedagogical sciences that form a specific group. These include the following:

General Pedagogy: Studies the conceptual issues and practical aspects of pedagogy.

Pedagogical Theory: Examines the general theoretical issues, laws, principles of pedagogy, and classification-related matters.

History of Pedagogy: Investigates the development of pedagogical thought, the historical features of schools and types of education, as well as their distinctive characteristics and significance.

Pedagogical Skill: Studies the tactics for effectively preparing teachers for pedagogical activity, the formation of pedagogical abilities, the development of pedagogical culture and techniques, as well as mastering speech techniques.

Preschool Education Pedagogy: Focuses on the education of children in preschool age, aiming to foster their intellectual, moral-ethical, and physical development.

Primary Education Pedagogy: This branch of pedagogy focuses on the education and upbringing of primary school students, studying their unique psychological and physiological characteristics, as well as addressing issues related to their intellectual, moral-ethical, and physical development.

Corrective (Special) Pedagogy: This field explores the issues related to the education and upbringing of children with physical or mental developmental disabilities. From this perspective, Article 20 of the Law on Education emphasizes Inclusive Education, which ensures equal opportunities for all learners to access education, taking into account their specific educational needs and individual capabilities. Inclusive education is organized in educational institutions for children (individuals) with physical, intellectual, sensory (perceptual), or mental disabilities. The procedure for organizing inclusive education is determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Future primary school teachers must have a solid knowledge of corrective pedagogy to effectively organize inclusive education.

Pedagogical Technology: This field investigates the application of modern pedagogical technologies in the teaching and upbringing process and examines methods to increase the effectiveness of education and upbringing through technological approaches. Today, pedagogical technologies are essential for achieving the educational and developmental goals of students.

Every future primary school teacher should expand the scope of implementing new pedagogical and information technologies into the educational process and apply advanced practices in this field.

Educational Management: This field studies the organization, management, control, and setting of future directions for the activities of educational institutions.

Social Pedagogy: This branch of pedagogy examines the socialization of the individual, the pedagogical diagnosis, correction, and rehabilitation of deviations from social norms, as well as the organization of social-pedagogical activities.

Family Pedagogy: This area focuses on family education, raising children in the family based on high moral-ethical qualities, and improving the pedagogical culture of parents.

Folk Pedagogy: Folk pedagogy encompasses the pedagogical knowledge preserved in oral traditions, customs, rituals, national and children's games, toys, and other elements of national upbringing and traditions.

Comparative Pedagogy: This branch of pedagogy studies the theory and practice of pedagogy in different countries, regions, and historical periods, examining their current state, development trends, and achievements from a comparative perspective.

Pedagogical Innovation: This field investigates the emergence and development of pedagogical innovations, ensuring the interrelation between pedagogical traditions and future educational projects.

Pedagogical Axiology: Pedagogical axiology is the study of educational values, focusing on the value of education from the perspective of the learner and the recognition of education as a value. It serves to establish an axiological approach to education and upbringing.

Neuro-pedagogy: Neuro-pedagogy is the practical field that explores the functional differences in the activities and structure of the brain (the right and left hemispheres) and applies this knowledge to the teaching and upbringing process.

Museum Pedagogy: Museum pedagogy is an interdisciplinary field formed by the convergence of pedagogy, psychology, and museology. It investigates methods of teaching and upbringing in the museum environment. A staff member specializing in this educational direction is known as a museum pedagogue.

Pedagogical Acmeology: This branch of pedagogy studies the professional development of teachers and the process of achieving the highest professional level. The term "acme" (from Greek "akme" – "the highest point") refers to "ascent" or "reaching the highest level." Pedagogical acmeology, therefore, focuses on studying the conditions, factors, and processes necessary for achieving high results in a teacher's professional activity.

Creative Pedagogy: Creative pedagogy refers to the ability of a teacher to create new ideas aimed at ensuring the effectiveness of the teaching and upbringing process, distinct from traditional pedagogical thinking, and also describes the teacher's readiness to solve existing pedagogical problems positively [6;10].

For future primary school teachers, it is essential to develop the skill of approaching each situation creatively, quickly and effectively solving problematic situations in a positive manner.

In particular, future primary school teachers will encounter the pedagogical sciences mentioned above during their professional activities. Every teacher must approach each student individually, considering their psychological state, abilities, and potential. To achieve this, teachers need to study psychology in-depth and approach each student's psychological state

consciously and thoughtfully, being aware of the various branches of psychology. Every teacher should be familiar with the following psychological areas:

General Psychology: This area investigates the general psychological laws, mechanisms, complex internal connections, theoretical and methodological principles, scientific research methods, as well as the phylogenetic and ontogenetic changes of the psyche, knowledge processes, and the scientific concepts and categories related to them.

Experimental Psychology: This field focuses on studying psychological phenomena using experimental methods. Experimental research has played a key role in psychology's separation from philosophy as a science. Researchers in experimental psychology have made significant contributions to the development of pedagogical psychology. Furthermore, the psychological directions that emerged during this period had a positive impact on the development of pedagogical psychology. The behavioral psychology direction laid the foundation for pedagogical psychology, emphasizing the influence of the external environment on educators and teachers. The more positive the external environment, the more favorable the educational development of an individual will be.

Pedagogical Psychology: This field of psychology examines the issues related to education and upbringing. Pedagogical psychology studies the psychological problems associated with the goal-oriented development of the individual, cognitive activities, and the formation of socially positive qualities in individuals. The aim of pedagogical psychology is to enhance the effective developmental influence of teaching, based on conditions and other psychological factors.

In modern pedagogical psychology, the development of the individual is understood in light of individual-psychological differences, the influence of socio-historical experience, and interactions with other people. This approach takes into account various factors in the development of the individual through educational practices.

Pedagogical psychology can be conditionally divided into several categories:

- a) Educational psychology
- b) Upbringing psychology
- c) Teacher psychology
- d) Higher education psychology, among others.

Sports Psychology: Sports psychology is the field of psychology that studies the development of human psyche during sports competitions and training activities, as well as the psychological laws of group relationships. This field began to develop rapidly in the 1960s and 1970s, with early research focusing on the individual-psychological differences among athletes. Nowadays, the scope of problems studied in sports psychology has expanded, and its main task is to create important conditions that influence athletes' psychological and physical development. In addition, sports psychology also provides psychological support to athletes in their personal development and achievements.

Family Psychology: Family psychology is an interdisciplinary field that focuses on the psychological issues of families. It studies the factors influencing the family, the distribution of roles within the family, marital relationships, interpersonal communication, age characteristics, and gender differences in communication. The materials gathered by family psychology are used to provide counseling for maintaining family stability and to develop sociological and

psychological programs. Additionally, family types, structures, hierarchies, and the objective and subjective factors affecting them are also within the scope of this field.

Management Psychology: This field studies the psychological laws of control, evaluation, and relationships within production activities involving individuals, groups, and teams in society, as well as the characteristics and abilities of leaders.

Differential Psychology: Differential psychology is the field of psychology that studies the psychological differences between individuals and the psychological aspects of discrepancies within groups, such as individual differences in abilities and characteristics [7;12].

The Importance of Pedagogical and Psychological Sciences in Developing Teachers' Professional Competencies:

Pedagogical Preparation: Pedagogical knowledge provides teachers with fundamental concepts on how to teach students, respond to their needs, and organize the learning process. This, in turn, helps teachers choose appropriate teaching methods, approaches, and learning techniques. Pedagogical sciences help teachers monitor students' knowledge and skills, promote their development, and apply effective teaching methods.

Psychological Preparation: Psychology enables teachers to understand the psychological state of students, recognize their needs, and develop pedagogical approaches that are tailored to each student's individual characteristics. Psychological knowledge helps teachers understand students' emotional states, motivation, learning methods, and abilities, while also supporting them in addressing psychological issues such as stress and supporting their emotional and psychological growth.

Individual Work with Students: For future primary school teachers, pedagogical and psychological knowledge teaches them to consider the individual characteristics of each student. This allows teachers to apply teaching methods that are adapted to each student. For example, some students may prefer visual learning, while others may be more aligned with kinesthetic or auditory learning styles. Pedagogical and psychological knowledge helps teachers select different learning methods to ensure each student's success in the learning process.

Supporting Students' Psychological Development: Pedagogical and psychological sciences allow teachers to monitor students' psychological development and take necessary actions to support it. This helps improve students' self-esteem, social relationships, and learning motivation. Teachers acquire skills to approach students' mental state collaboratively, understand their social and psychological needs, and establish positive relationships with them.

Creativity and Innovation: Pedagogical and psychological sciences teach teachers to think creatively, learn new pedagogical technologies, and organize the learning process of students effectively using modern methods. This encourages teachers to apply creative and innovative pedagogical approaches. Based on pedagogical and psychological knowledge, teachers become ready to support students' new ideas, and develop and apply modern methods of teaching.

The integration of pedagogy and psychology plays a crucial role in successfully organizing meaningful education and the teaching process. Pedagogical skills and psychological knowledge together are essential for taking into account students' individual characteristics and organizing the teaching process optimally. At the same time, pedagogical competence depends not only on theoretical knowledge but also on practical experience and personal development. To improve the quality of the education system, higher education institutions should pay special attention to integrating pedagogical and psychological knowledge for students. Implementing creative

approaches in education, increasing teachers' readiness to create innovative ideas, and applying pedagogical technologies are essential for making the learning process more effective. This, in turn, requires the regular updating of primary school teachers' knowledge and skills. In this context, it is important to further strengthen the significance of pedagogical and psychological knowledge as a result of teachers' practices and ongoing reforms in education. This will help raise teachers' professional competence and enhance their effectiveness in teaching students.

Conclusion: The research conducted shows that acquiring and integrating pedagogical and psychological knowledge is vital for future primary school teachers. The study demonstrates that the integration of pedagogical and psychological sciences should consider the specific characteristics of each learning period and its applicability in practice. Specifically, focusing on the quality of training in pedagogical fields, ensuring high professional preparation for future primary school teachers, developing their pedagogical skills, and constantly improving their pedagogical and psychological knowledge are essential. Teachers should approach each pedagogical and psychological branch with awareness of these disciplines. The integration of pedagogy and psychology is a necessary tool for making the teaching process more effective. This not only plays a significant role in preparing students for knowledge but also in preparing them for life. Therefore, mastering pedagogical and psychological knowledge and applying it in practice is of paramount importance.

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